

CO-DESIGNING WITH COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

Today co-design is mostly intended as the activity that enables new collaborative relations between end users and designers. Many researchers in design (Sanders, 2006; Binder and Brandt, 2008; Westerlund, 2007; Mattelmaki, 2005) have conducted *design experiments* to test the effectiveness of the tools designed to support end users participation in design processes. Moreover co-design with customers has become an approach to the project for many design firms (Brown, 2008).

The paper reports the authors' experience with co-design in 4 different companies. All the cases presented have been planned as an opportunity of interaction between different actors from companies and external professional designers. Each of the design interventions has been conducted to boost innovation processes in companies with the aim to encompass the difficulties that people with an everyday contact with a problem find in expressing an innovative point of view on it.

The analysis of the cases pointed out that co-design with company seems to diverge from co-design with end users for the aims pursued, the tools used and the role that designers play in it. In particular, co-design with company seems to be more focused on designing new business models and envisioning innovation as a dynamic and systematic change at each level of the company; co-design with company is better supported by tools that boost envisioning (scenarios, trends analysis, promising cases) and support representatives from the different company internal divisions to discuss together; designers are sources of inspiration for the employees, they act as triggers of innovation more than as facilitators of the co-design process.

Keywords: co-design, design processes, design competence and knowledge

INTRODUCTION¹

Co-design, intended as the phenomenon of having end-users directly involved in the process of development of new concepts and innovations is one of most studied issue in design research as the practiced way to foster user driven innovation (Brown 2008). In fact it is possible to observe a huge amount of design literature dealing with co-design in terms of its general definition and its proliferation (Sanders, 2006; Binder and Brandt, 2008) whose main contributions can be summarized as follows:

- research in analysing co-design phenomenon concentrates its attention on the end user's role as the fundamental unit of analysis (Sander and Stapper; 2008; Vaajakallio and Mattelmäki 2007);
- co-design is intended as an activity that occur among end users, designed by designers to inspire and inform the design process (Botero, Mattelmaki, Rizzo, 2008; Rizzo, 2010);
- workshop is the most applied tool to organize a co-design session (Westerlund, 2007; Keinonen, Jaasko, Mattlmaki, 2008);
- co-design is a topic that characterizes design research since a long time. During 40 years of research the idea of designing FOR users has evolved into the idea of designing WITH users, which underlines the changes in the role that users play in design processes: from information source, to content provider, to co-designers (Björgvinsson, Ehn, Per-Anders Hillgren, 2010);
- this evolution corresponds to a change in the role of users' studies in the design process: from a preliminary activity to be conducted in order to provide information for the design process (users requirements and specifications), to a sort of

¹ This paper is a reflection on a series of consultant experiences in companies and it has to be considered a joint effort from both authors. Nevertheless, Alessandro Deserti has directly edited sessions 3 (and sub-session 3.3, 3.4), 4 and 5. Francesca Rizzo edited sessions 1, 2, sub-sessions 3.1, 3.2.

inspirational activity mainly conducted to brainstorm with end users to envisioning innovations.

Even though powerful and interesting (especially for the effort spent on design methods and techniques) this production lacks of an understanding of the strategic role that co-design plays when it occurs in companies and it is led by design. In these conditions co-design shows different characteristics: (i) it is a design process that takes place among experts: professional designers and people that have a specific expertise on the company production processes, sector, knowledge, style, market, aims, mission and vision; (ii) it often applies to (or results in) the design of new business models for the company; (iii) designers act as triggers of innovation and co-design process leads to a mediation among the conflicting needs and constraints that come from the environment external to the company. If we compare co-design with end users to co-design with a company, we can say that both process typologies are designed and conducted by professional designers and involve people that does not held specific design knowledge. At the same time the two typologies diverge for the goals that they peruse as well as for the role that designers play in. In the first case co-design aims to inspire the design process in terms of which new products/services can be designed to make them available for end-users effective, satisfactory, wow experiences (Vainio-Mattila et alii, 2011). Under this typology we find the cases mostly described in the UCD literature, here the designer acts as a facilitator and an expert of a series techniques used to stimulate end-users participation. Designers are the experts who design tools for supporting participation and conversation (Rizzo, 2010), and they are those who re-elaborate collected suggestions in possible design ideas. In the second case company exploits co-design process with designers to foster collaboration with experts in innovation, to bring in new visions or to boost innovation at the level of their strategic choices and business models. These design processes are usually conducted by designers in a company/institution (engaging employees or internal divisions) looking for new solutions to be implemented. The aim of these kinds of processes is to force out-of-the-box thinking in situations where the deep knowledge and the familiarity with the solutions inhibit innovation. Here designers are triggers of new visions that boost the company reflection on strategic changes. Designers are the

sources of inspiration for the company, the visionaries who figure out scenarios and design trajectories, making them available as "subjects of discussion" of the co-design process.

This paper focuses on 4 cases of workshops of co-design conducted in 4 different companies (3 Italian and 1 Brazilian) by enrolling designers and company employees in co-designing innovation solutions. The paper is organized as follows: session 2 introduces co-design literature and presents a discussion about how co-design has been modeled and experimented in the field of UCD; session 3 presents the idea that when co-design is conducted between professional designers and a company it shows a different model (with respect to that implemented in co-designing between designers and end-users). The session then tries to demonstrate this assumption analyzing 4 selected cases. Session 4 discusses some general statements derived from cases analysis and points out some implications for considering co-design in companies contexts as a design-led process of mediation where design plays a double role: it is the trigger of the process and its source of inspiration, bringing in creativity and lateral thinking and visions; it is the actor that holds the competence to conduct and mediate the process by designing tools, bringing in the process specific competences about the mediation of different needs and conflicts that may emerge during the process.

CO-DESIGN IN DESIGN LITERATURE: THE CURRENT MODEL

The attempt to bring end users into the design process has been the core objective of User-Centered Design. In different domain of applications and for different aims this design method has integrated users research and testing techniques in design processes basically to pursue the idea of "good design" that means making products and services that are really effective to support people in their activities (from learning to playing, from cooking to working, from travelling to wellbeing). In these contexts "users" have been treated as a variable to be investigated and observed to derive user requirements that would turn the design project in good design (Cross, 2007, Margolin and Buchanan, 1995).

Today co-design, intended as those design activities that occur between designers and end-users to make new solutions for end-users problems, represents one of the most investigated issue and design research community is discussing whether it represents a new

and emergent design method to deal with end users or a new technique that is based on a modification of the role of end user in design process.

From a more fundamental human-centered design point of view, the main challenge of co-design is to enable users' innovation potential. Many experiments of co-design are taking the form of explorative workshops designed to involve users in relative long and intensive process of creative activities (Wersterlund, 2007; Binder and Brandt, 2008) during which they are "required" to design that means that they perform activities based on manipulating things, express ideas, make paper mock-up and low fidelity prototypes of what they figured out. Even though users are contributing in a variety of ways, they almost exclusively respond to designers' proposals visualized in probes and tools projected to stimulate and support people "making dimension" (Sanders, 2006), contributing to solution generation, for instance by participating in prototyping, storytelling, scenarios building and evaluations (Vaajakallio and Mattelmaki, 2007). Co-design in the human centred framework serves designers in idea generation by providing insights and inspiration.

Today many co-design projects are practically organized through workshops used as open platforms for bringing end users in the design process.

Workshops can be described as the basic model of co-design process. They can be also defined as an inquiry into a future situation of use for potential end users.

Basic workshops are often designed as a repository of different exercises that people are required to perform by using different tools for half a day or an entire day. Tools are designed ad hoc for the purpose of stimulating end users participation or are what emerges from co-design activity (Brandt 2006, 2008 calls design materials "Things-to-think-with" and Sanders and Stapper, 2008, uses "Make tools" for engaging people during intense workshops).

Participants to the workshop take part as themselves, not as representatives for their work position, a group of people with similar disabilities or so. Often participants are required to focus on real and recent situations and activities that relies with the topic of the workshop and experiences that they regard as meaningful for all start to become the

basis to generate ideas for improvements of the situations/activities. For the ideas that are regarded as the best ones the participants can make some meaningful representation (for example scenarios, storyboard, maps).

The method works best if the participants are engaged in several workshops that are held some time after each other.

Here designers perform as professionals, defining the tools that boost and help people participation; and as researchers/facilitators when they conduct co-design process. In this last role designers are expert in supporting people in expressing their ideas and opinion, as well as their wishes and needs; at the same time, they are expert in analyzing the materials obtained from the workshops in meaningful trajectories (ideas, inspirations, suggestions).

CO-DESIGN WITH COMPANIES: AN EMERGENT MODEL FROM 4 REAL CASES ANALYSIS

Literature on managerial sciences (Cheesbrough, 2003, Verganti, 2009) as well as from literature on design processes and competences (Deserti, 2009) has pointed out as innovation does not held value per se (or only for end users) but it depends on the strong relation that exists between innovation design and the need for a company (or a market) to envision radical changes, figure out new valuable opportunities, develop new business models: in other words to on boost innovation.

Despite these efforts for organizations with a strong culture it is very hard to grow or even detect innovations. Employees share the same beliefs about what the value proposition is and how to sustain it and it can be difficult to enroll them in new visions internally and draw company attention on new ideas. The set of techniques and models that seems to offer a new span of innovation relies in the design practice and in its integration with business model functioning and structure (Bucolo, 2011). The work of Schön (1983) and Polyanyi (1998) has formed the foundation of the Design Led Innovation model as a creative approach that can help people in companies to:

- overcome their organisational and cultural dogmas and beliefs;
- see the big picture and discovering new customers' insights and latent needs;

- visualise alternative value propositions and business models.

Central to this approach is the ability of the designer to construct and visualize multiple futures of an unknown complexity, which are then deconstructed to reveal needs and opportunities (Madhavan, R., Grover, 1998).

The underlines assumption under this statement is that design can lead innovation process in complex contests where the object to be designed is not a well-defined product or service (a punctual solution) but the realization of a strategic change.

In this session we present 4 different applications of co-design processes in companies. Cases have been selected applying the following criteria:

- representing examples of application of design tools and methodologies for co-design in real industrial contexts;
- aiming at envisioning changes and innovation at overcoming organisations dogma;
- aiming to achieve these results activating high levels of employees' participation.

We use the case described here to derive some results that support us to argument, in the next session, an emergent model of co-design process that bring with it at least two different and important phenomena:

- the notion of co-design as a design led process to envisioning innovation in terms of dynamic and systematic changes at each of the level of the company (not only on the side of end-users' experiences);
- the extension of the role of the designer in these kind of design processes: from facilitator to trigger of innovation.

BUSINESS MODEL INNOVATION THROUGH DESIGN LED INNOVATION: AN EXPERIENCE FROM THE MACHINERY INDUSTRY

Case context

The company faced in recent years a consistent decline in sales of machinery due to global competition and market conditions and it was forced to re-thing its strategy and business model. The fundamental challenge was the one of developing a consistent line of business through services. One of the most critical aspects in designing this change was in the strong manufacturing culture of the company

and the fundamentally technical and mechanical background of most of the employees. These aspects made it very difficult for the company to "see" a different future and a different way to make its earnings. The experience of a machinery manufacturer in Italy offered the opportunity to design a co-design workshop series to test a set of design tools for business model design and innovation and verify the quality of the output.

The solution that the company decided to choose to overcome these difficulties was based on the massive involvement of a large part of the employees (150 people) in a series of ten innovation workshops aimed at co-designing together with a team of designers possible business models for new service business.

Workshop aims, structure and tools

The series of co-design workshops should conduct company and its employee to design innovative business models with a clear perception of the changes required and the constraints to overcome. Workshops have been structured in two days. The first one has been devoted to overcoming organizational dogmas and envisioning the future; the second one focused on co-designing a possible business model for the service business. The techniques that have been adopted in the different phases are related to: scenario building and storytelling in the first day to generate insights related to the needs and expectations of customers and overcome dogmas limiting the ability to see customers and their needs under a different perspective; business model definition through the use of the model proposed by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2009) in the second day.

Results

The results of the set of workshops could be evaluated under different aspects.

In terms of impact on corporate culture and better customer understanding, it could be outlined the fact that all participants were able to define their limits in looking at customer needs. This understanding of the limited perception of the customer expectations and deep needs brought motivated participants to devote particular efforts to the identification of a wide set of customer insights that were used as the backbone for the definition of the value proposition of new services and the business model underlying them. The broader vision of the customer experience that was generated

through different techniques (such the Empathy Map for the insight generation and the story telling technique to support a process view of customer behavior) during the workshops allowed participants to identify radically new area of opportunities for the company. The participants were split in three groups and each group dealt with a different set of customer segments that the company identified as possible targets for the new service offer.

Figure 2 - storytelling

Figure 3 - the Empathy Map

The needs identified in the first part of the workshops led to a very rich variety of business models to support the service offering. Each workshop produced three different business models, one for each customer segment. Business model formulation contained: value proposition; customer segments; channel definition; customer relationship model; sources of revenues and revenue models; key activities; assets needed; partners need to create and deliver the service. All this led to the evaluation of possible revenues and the cost structure needed to create it. Despite the fact that the participants were not familiar with the concept of business model the outcome was very satisfactory under many

aspects: All the groups were able to complete the business model in all its parts; the resource need and allocation was analyzed and described in detail; new forms of pricing and avenue generation were explored and draw to some very unexpected lines of possible business; a quantitative effort was common to all the groups.

Figure - 4 Samples of the business models generated

The company was then able to review all the business models proposed, the need categories detected and draw a new possible line of business overcoming the constraints that did not allow management to clearly see the market for services and plan an adequate offer. Among the different business model proposed some of the most innovative for the industry could be described as follow:

- creating temporary workshops with machineries for very specific productions. These workshops could be moved in order to allow companies to use the machineries for a short period of time and obtain assistance and information from specialized personnel. The payment system is based on renting the machinery or on the kind of production requested. This solution allows small companies to develop their business without acquiring expensive machineries and skilled personnel.
- Offering a portal for creating a global market for second hand machineries guaranteed by the manufacturer. In this case, the value proposition relies upon the chance to increase machinery turnover for large companies that could have a guaranteed price for second hand machineries and, on the other hand, allow small companies or companies in emerging markets to access quality used machineries revised and controlled by the original manufacturer that could also support

conservation in mobility, modular refrigeration in small communities, unconventional food conservation (ethnic food, typical recipes, etc.) and special care for highly perishable goods in mobility (make ups, beauty creams, pharmaceutical products, etc.) and the role of the refrigerator as a communication and life management support.

Figure 7 - The concept generation

The third way was devoted to idea generation of product or service concepts to help the people depicted in the scenarios to better perform their activity eliminating or reducing the constraints and burdens described the previous day. This activity led to the identification of four different product solutions to better perform the tasks depicted in the storyboards.

Results

The company collected during the three days a set of very valuable inputs from the different groups that could be summarized as follow:

- New ways of segmenting and approaching the market. The description of the different micro scenarios and the trends that originated them was crucial to re-think company present segmentation criteria and insight identification.
- Generation of new product and service concepts that helped the company in overcoming its limits in the idea generation in the conservation business. In particular, the workshop outputs led

managers of the company to direct their investments in smaller devices, more task focused and aimed at differently segmented customer base. In particular, the different concepts could be synthesized in the following way:

- A membrane that could be hosted in the fridge where it absorbs the chill. When travelling this membrane could be picked out of the fridge and adapted to any kind of luggage. When in the new destination the membrane could be folded and put into another fridge to recharge.
- A modular refrigeration box that could be attached to a skeleton containing the electric engine. In this case different refrigeration modules could be combined together offering different temperature and components to adapt to the needs of different people share the hull and the energy. This system was also the solution for the special conservation needs scenario, though in this case the components were not modular but could have different sizes and features depending on the specific situation and needs.
- The fridge has a cover that could be customized to fit the needs of a specific individual or family. This cover could host some other appliances like the coffee machine, be a dock for recharging other devices and even host a screen to interact with different electronic devices to sync them while having breakfast or during a late night snack.

INNOVATING HOME FURNITURE: DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW BRAND AND PRODUCT-SERVICE SYSTEM

Case context

Brinna is a new Brazilian home furniture brand, part of MD Móveis Group, located in Rio Grande do Sul. At the time when the project started (November 2005), the company was producing unbranded products, positioned in the mid-low segment of the market, and was developing the awareness that this segment would be in a nearby future completely controlled by the organized distribution, which was already leaving very small margins to producers, making them compete just on price.

The company asked our research group to guide a cultural transformation, shifting from the capability

to operate in a traditional industrial environment to the capability of interpreting a post-industrial context.

Project structure

The request from the company was turned into a long-term cooperation project (5 years), with an intensive first phase (2 years) structured in sequential and concurrent steps. The first step consisted in the construction of a long-term strategy, based on the development of a portfolio of brands with different competitive aims, stretching from mid-low to high-end segments of the market, and on the introduction of design knowledge and competences inside the company. The second step of the project consisted in the development of a R&D department, characterized by an advanced model of interaction between functional areas, which were put in the same space to make them exchange knowledge and ideas, and work together from the early stages of the development of the new products. The third step consisted in the development of the first new brand, in terms of opportunities, positioning, values, expected characteristics of products, and defined in terms of visual identity. The fourth step consisted in a wide research, meant as a tool to nurture the development of new products.

Figure 8 - Research structure and main steps

The fifth step consisted in the development of the initial product portfolio, which was structured through a workshop involving young designers: the basic idea was that our institution should not get in competition with professionals, but integrate them offering opportunities. The subsequent steps, not

described here, were finalized to the transformation of conceptual ideas in solutions, and the establishment of a production and retail system.

Workshop aims, structure and tools

The workshop involved 25 young designers, supported by 4 experts with a wide experience in the sector. The conduction of the workshop was highly structured, and did not start with a "normal" brief, but with the presentation of a preliminary research, conducted in 6 months, synthesized in 3 dossiers delivered to all the participants:

- company and market research dossier, whose main aim was to define the technological and market framework (capabilities of the company, competitors, peculiar characteristics of market etc.);
- blue-sky research dossier, whose main aim was to provide a set of innovation pathways and inspirational references, in form of scenarios and moodboards;
- brand-identity research dossier, whose main aim was to provide guidelines to designers on the new brand, which was still not existing.

Figure 9 - One of the inspiration boards

The design brief was thus a synthesis of the dossiers, defining specific requests to designers in terms of expected products. The goal of the workshop was to develop conceptual solutions of new products, starting from the system of constraints and opportunities described in the dossiers. The workshop was conducted in a 2 months period during which designers were organized in teams, free to organize their time except for 6 reviews with experts, giving technical support on the development

of products. Reviews were organized as seminars, so that each team could interact with the other teams and with the experts, exchanging ideas and stimulating both a cooperative and a competitive attitude.

Results

The result was the development of nearly one hundred ideas for new products, in the form of conceptual designs, ranging from simple freestanding object to more complex systems and families of objects.

Figure 10 - One of the conceptual solutions (Alberti, Colombo)

Most of the products presented innovative characteristics, more on the form and use sides rather than on the technological one, since one of the assumptions was to use traditional technologies that the company already possessed or could easily acquire.

The final presentation involved the owners of the company, but was not intended as a gate in a linear process: the application of a typical funnel model, such as Cooper's stage-gate, was refused in the early steps of the project, considering that it would create a contradiction between efficiency and capability of sustaining creativity and innovation.

Figure 11 - One of the final products

The selection of the concepts passed by a prototyping phase, conducted in the following months by the company with the help of designers and prototypists, representing the first nucleus of the R&D department. The prototyping phase gave a

better understanding of what could be immediately produced, and what would need revisions or improvement of production capabilities. Almost no solution was discarded, since the general idea was that all the innovative conceptual solutions could be useful, and that the problem was not just to select the ones that would have gone on to the further step of development, but to build a "shelf innovation" approach, preserving solutions that could be adopted in the future.

INNOVATING PRODUCT DESIGN AS A MEAN TO INNOVATE AN ORGANIZATION

Case context

Gardesa S.p.A., now part of the Assa Abloy Group, is one of the biggest Italian producers of security doors. Gardesa commissioned to our design research group an applied research project, willing to introduce innovations in a sector where, according to the point of view of its CEO, "nothing new happened in the last 20 years". The project was thus concentrated on the development of new products, but its strategic aim was to introduce design capabilities in a company mainly focalized on production and characterized by a limited product-service system innovation attitude.

Project structure

The project started with the development of a wide preliminary research, as a tool to nurture the design of innovative products, to be conducted in a workshop, involving young designers, experts, internal and external stakeholders.

The research started with the construction of a few scenarios, turned into possible pathways, which could be followed to innovate. Scenarios were built imagining possible futures for the product (the security door as a service, the security door as a piece of furniture; the security door as a technical accessory etc.), through the qualitative interpretation of strong and weak signals.

In the research, the typical bi-dimensional nature of the product was somehow neglected: the security door was interpreted as part of an environment, defining the complex border between inside and outside. Meanwhile, the idea of security, stereotypically assumed in the sector as the only possible value to be communicated and the only function to be exploited, was confronted with the idea of freedom. According to the results of interviews conducted with end-users, security was perceived as a sort of commodity: customers

imagined that the door would surely be secure, and there was no point in explaining it in a technical way, also because in the normal classes of security a door would resist to a burglar's attack for 2-5 minutes, which did not seem a point that would make any customer at ease.

The results of the research were turned into "innovation corridors", described in terms of possible futures for the product and the company.

Workshop aims, structure and tools

The workshop involved 20 young designers, organized in 7 teams, and was conducted during a 4 months period. The workshop started with a seminar, where the company introduced its case and brief, while researchers presented their preliminary work to participants.

Figure 12 - Research topics

The research dossier given to designers consisted in a wide system of information and tools meant to feed the design process, providing insights on the context (competitors, possible technologies, rules and limitations), on possible innovation pathways (future scenarios), on references and motifs of inspiration (inspirational moodboards, opening/closing systems in different fields, security doors in sci-fi movies, etc.). The workshop was structured as an interaction activity, where all the participants joined 8 collective meetings in a place external to the company, and 2 meetings inside the company involving stakeholders. During the meetings, design teams interacted among them, explaining their ideas through sketches and preliminary visualizations of solutions, and with researchers and an expert of product engineering. This way, a "concurrent" process of development, considering both innovation perspectives and

production possibilities, was carried on, and was presented to the company as an example of the possible "philosophy" of organization of the R&D department.

Results

The main result of the project was the establishment of an R&D department in the company, now run by one of the young designers who participated in the workshop.

The project expanded the value of the Gardesa brand, later acquired by Assa Abloy when the property decided to retire, considering among its intangible assets the capability to integrate design in the innovation process, which is an unconventional attitude in the mechanical sector, normally focused on technology and production.

Figure 13 - One of the conceptual solutions (Baglieri, Bertoli, Costacurta)

The result of the workshop was a set of conceptual ideas, presenting radical and incremental innovations, in fact much wider than the immediate development possibilities of the company, meant to feed the R&D department for the next years. The workshop showed the possibility of using design thinking and capabilities to deploy unconventional points of view, build new perspectives, and develop innovative ideas.

Interesting "side results" were the development of a much more advanced system of communication, based on the new idea of "freedom vs. security", and the development of a service design project, subsequently turned into the "Gardesa assistance" pack of services, which solved many problems in the relation with installers and end-users, and gave a tough contribution to customers' satisfaction.

Figure 14 - One of the final products

CASES DISCUSSION AND LESSON LEARNT

What seems to emerge is that when applied in companies' contexts, co-design processes occur in different ways than as it usually happens between end-users and designers, and it produce different results.

As general reflections we observed four main characteristics:

- all of the cases analyzed show co-design is characterized by a design process conducted to figure out strategic changes for the company, in particular to define new business models.
- Co-design with companies, in the cases examined, has the aim to overcome companies' dogma that often prevent the management as well as employees to be creative.
- Co-design tools used to support processes in the cases reported play the role of representing "subjects" of discussion for the co-designers (in the forms of possible futures, or trajectories that could be followed) more than the role of facilitating the participants' self-expression. They are dossier of trends, promising cases that act as cool-hunting tools, canvases² that help to think in a systemic way to new business models.
- In the cases examined designers held the role of professionals who were required to be bring in the co-design activity their own vision on the problem faced (co-design tools), and to share them with people who have competences on the feasibility and the realization of these ideas. At the same time they act as triggers of innovation,

forcing co-designers to go further current internal processes, seriously considering the possibility of introducing new ideas, changes in the company's vision or positioning in the market.

Looking in particular each of the cases reported, we observed what follows. In the security doors workshop two of the mid-reviews took the form of a presentation of early conceptual solutions to stakeholders: technicians of production, the external communication agency, a group of selected retailers. These stakeholders ideally represented the value chain, and gave the opportunity of considering the company not just as a punctual entity, but as complex system of connections in the form of a network, as Normann and Ramirez (1993) would put it. The interaction with these stakeholders was important not just to have different feedbacks, but also to force designers to look for innovation through all the value chain: not just new products, but also new forms of communication, service, presence in the distribution.

In the furniture company workshop physical interaction with stakeholders was not possible, due to long geographical distance, but it was substituted by a "role play" action, where experts acted in the roles of stakeholders, bringing in problems and points of view, focusing and guiding the co-design process, reconciling user needs with business goals through a mix of empirical research and structured, measured data.

In the machinery company workshop all the functions were represented during the sessions allowing different design models to emerge and different perspectives and cultures to merge together and offer a richer understanding of the managerial implications of the different business models designed. The design approach allowed people to think in terms of systems and relationship. Here designers brought both a mindset or characteristic way of seeing the world and an associated toolkit of relevant skills and competencies.

In the case of the household appliance company, the intervention of an external group of designers coming from a different company (a shoes company) with a radically different background challenged the R&D team ideas and beliefs bringing new approaches and perspectives in customer definition and understanding, and in shifting the focus of workshop on context of use more than on technology. Here designers from another company helped people

² Canvas is a tool designed by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2009) to facilitate the processo f new business model design. It represents the different components of a business model in a whole underlines the importance of applying a holistic and sistemi point of view in designing innovation.

to consider opportunities and not just constraints, introducing innovation possibilities inside the characteristics of the company (products portfolio, production processes, people competences, suppliers network etc.).

CONCLUSION

The cases discussed in this paper allow us to introduce a different point of view on co-design when it occurs between professional designers and a company. In these cases in fact it seems to take the form of a design led process, simultaneously focusing on user needs and business objectives, which can create value both for customers and companies. At the same time the cases analysis showed another important element: the extended role that designers' must play in this kind of processes. Here designers are more than facilitators or professionals required to design tools to help participants to express their creativity. Here designers are asked to declare their point of view and visions by designing those artifacts (dossiers, promising cases, trajectories of possible and viable solutions, scenarios of envisioning) that address and lead co-design process.

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